

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION TO BASIC METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITE
STRUCTURAL HARDWARE FOR LAUNCH VEHICLE APPLICATIONS

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Several aspects of the fabrication and characterization activities currently under development at NETCO for Navy Launch Vehicle Application will be discussed. The status of several advanced composite fabrication processes for unidirectional continuous graphite fiber composites to be reviewed include uniaxial hot pressing, hot isostatic compaction and creep forming.

Results obtained from aluminum alloys reinforced with discontinuous silicon carbide whiskers and chopped glass fibers fabricated by conventional metal-working techniques will be presented. These techniques include the preparation of composite ingots using advanced pressure casting techniques followed by conventional elevated temperature extrusion and rolling operations.

Problems encountered during the fabrication and characterization of various graphite-aluminum systems will be discussed in some detail. These include development of the necessary tooling to fabricate basic structural shapes such as hat and zee stiffeners and tubular elements. Results from parametric studies to define the time, temperature and pressure parameters necessary to effect complete consolidation without internal cracking in graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloy composites will be presented.

Data from characterization studies including both nondestructive and destructive examinations will be summarized. These data include the development of radiographic and C-Scan ultrasonic inspection techniques for both continuous and discontinuous fiber reinforced aluminum alloys. A correlation of the NDT results with the resultant mechanical properties and microstructural observations will be presented. NETCO experience in the use of quality control standards for establishing baseline inspection techniques will be presented. The difficulties of designing, fabricating and using a variety of baseline graphite-aluminum quality control standards for ultrasonic C-Scan inspections will be discussed. Typical results obtained from monolayer, bi-layer and baseline (Tri-layer) Thornel 50/201 Aluminum alloy laminate sheet structures will be reviewed. The development of ultrasonic C-Scan procedures to inspect basic Gr/Al structural shapes such as hat and zee sections will be discussed in detail.

The paper will discuss the variations in intentionally fabricated defects of the standard panel and the sensitivity required in the ultrasonic inspection equipment to detect subtle manufacturing defects.